

Words in Simple Words

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Abstract

This article serves as a practical, concise, and easily understandable guide for English language learners and teachers. It provides a clear understanding of which vocabulary to focus on, what it means to know a word, how to learn or teach words, and how to assess form-meaning vocabulary knowledge. The study offers a brief and straightforward manual to improve vocabulary knowledge, using language that is accessible even to English language learners with low proficiency.

Keywords: high and low-frequency words; vocabulary knowledge; vocabulary learning; vocabulary testing

Introduction

Knowing a word involves grasping its meaning. Learners typically consider a word known once they know both its form (how it sounds and looks) and its meaning (Nation, 2022). However, merely knowing the form and meaning may leave them struggling to use words in context, as there is more to learning words than just their form and meaning.

Research indicates that not all words are equally important to learn (Schmitt, 2008; Laufer & Ravenhorst-Kalovski, 2010; Schmitt & Schmitt, 2014). When setting vocabulary learning goals, it is advisable to focus on the most common words (Nation, 2022) and decide what aspects to learn about those words. Carefully selecting a set of words and understanding what to learn about them can significantly enhance learners' comprehension of the texts and conversations they encounter.

Literature should highlight essential words and various aspects of vocabulary knowledge beyond mere form-meaning connections. While the literature addresses these requirements, there is a need for an easy-to-understand and practical manual to assist learners and help teachers create an effective action plan. This study aims to fill that gap, providing English language learners and teachers with a concise guide to enhancing vocabulary learning and teaching, using simple language that even low-proficiency language learners can grasp.

Word Frequency (Family)

Words can be grouped into 1,000 frequency levels, called word families, based on how often they are used. Nation (2006) organized vocabulary from the British National Corpus (BNC) into

twenty 1,000-word frequency levels. The BNC is a huge 100 million-word collection from written and spoken sources (BNC official website, 2022).

Research on word frequency shows that some words are more important than others (see Schmitt, 2008; Laufer & Ravenhorst-Kalovski, 2010, and Schmitt & Schmitt, 2014). Therefore, when setting vocabulary learning goals, the best strategy is mastering the most common words (Nation, 2022). An analysis of the texts and conversations that learners may encounter shows that carefully choosing certain words can boost their understanding. Nation (2006) found that about 3,000 to 4,000 word families cover 95 percent of a text's content, while 6,000 to 9,000 word families are needed for 98 percent coverage (see Table 1). This 98 percent goal is supported by research (Hu & Nation, 2000; Schmitt et al., 2011; van Zeeland & Schmitt, 2013) and represents a reasonable amount of unfamiliar vocabulary to learn.

Table 1
English vocabulary sizes needed to get 95 and 98 percent coverage (including proper nouns) of various kinds of texts

Texts	95% coverage	98% coverage	Proper nouns
Novels	4,000 word families	9,000 word families	1–2%
Newspapers	4,000 word families	8,000 word families	5–6%
Children’s movies	4,000 word families	6,000 word families	1.5%
Spoken English	3,000 word families	7,000 word families	1.3%

Source: *Learning vocabulary in another language*, Nation (2022, p.16)

Word Types

Words can be grouped into three main frequency levels. These levels are high-frequency (the most frequent 3,000 words), mid-frequency (6,000 words from the fourth to the ninth 1,000-word groups), and low-frequency (the tenth 1,000 words and beyond). Nation and Coxhead (2021) use the metaphor of a tree to explain how vocabulary grows in native speakers. In this comparison, the roots stand for high-frequency words, the trunk stands for mid-frequency words, and the branches include low-frequency words. These low-frequency words cover specialized technical terms and vocabulary associated with specific professions or interests.

High-frequency Words

High-frequency words include function words such as 'on,' 'a,' 'and' 'the,' and numerous content words such as 'paper,' 'talk,' 'young,' and 'slowly.' According to Nation (2022), around 80 percent of text words fall into the high-frequency category. Schmitt and Schmitt (2014) recommend embracing a high-frequency vocabulary of 3,000 word families, which typically accounts for about 95 percent of text content (Nation, 2006). It is advised to master the top 3,000 word families from the Nation's BNC/COCA¹ lists (2020), recognized as extensively researched high-

¹ The British National Corpus (BNC) and the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA)

frequency word lists (Dang & Webb, 2014; Dang et al., 2020). These lists are accessible in [Paul Nation's repository](#). For an effective acquisition of these word lists, exploring the "4000 Essential English Words" book series (volumes 1 to 3), second edition, written by Paul Nation, is highly recommended.

Mid-frequency Words

The second category of words is called mid-frequency words. There are 6,000 of these words in BNC/COCA lists, from the fourth 1,000 to the ninth 1,000 words. They are generally practical and moderately frequent. They are also versatile and can be used in many different contexts. A list of mid-frequency words is available on [Paul Nation's repository](#). Research shows that knowing the top 9,000 most frequent words, which includes high-frequency and mid-frequency words (3,000 + 6,000), will allow you to understand about 98% of all text (Nation, 2006). These words are important for understanding spoken and written English and are consistent across different text types (Sorell, 2013).

Low-frequency Words

Low-frequency words are the least common words in English, and they go beyond the most common 9,000 words. There are about 40,000 of these words (Nation, 2022), and they are often specialized or technical terms (words related to interests and professions). Technical words are important for understanding specific fields and can be learned by consulting experts in those fields. Teachers should only teach low-frequency words when essential for understanding a text or relevant to a specific context. Learners can learn low-frequency words intentionally but often pick them up through incidental exposure when reading and listening.

Academic Words

Academic vocabulary is important for language learners who want to succeed in academia. For them, it is a subset of high-frequency vocabulary commonly used in academic texts. There are two well-researched academic vocabulary lists: the Academic Word List (AWL, Coxhead, 2000) and the Academic Vocabulary List (AVL, Gardner & Davies, 2014). The word lists for both AWL and AVL are accessible on the [EAP Foundation website](#) under the Vocab tab. While both the AWL and AVL offer valuable vocabulary, Nation (2022) emphasizes that the AWL may introduce more unfamiliar terms to those not well-versed in academic content. For learners with immediate academic needs, the AWL is particularly beneficial. Recommended resources for mastering the AWL include "Focus on Vocabulary 2: Mastering the Academic Word List" by Diana and Norbert Schmitt and the second edition of "4000 Essential English Words" book series (volume 4) by Paul Nation.

Developing an Academic Spoken Word List (ASWL) has also gained significant attention in recent years. Dang, Coxhead, and Webb (2017) crafted an ASWL, utilizing a corpus compiled from diverse academic environments, encompassing lectures, seminars, labs, and tutorials to address this need. The ASWL can be accessed on [Stuart Webb's repository](#).

Vocabulary Knowledge

According to Nation (2022), understanding vocabulary involves four interconnected elements: size or breadth, which refers to the number of words one is familiar with; depth, which refers to having a comprehensive understanding of various aspects related to knowing a word; strength, which encompasses the level of proficiency, including fluency and systematic comprehension, for each aspect of a word; integration, which evaluates how effectively knowledge of different words is interconnected.

In simpler terms, improving your vocabulary happens by learning more words (Size), knowing each word thoroughly (Depth), becoming proficient and fluent in using them (Strength), and connecting and integrating your knowledge of different words (Integration).

Knowing a Word

Words are not just separate items in a language; they are connected in different ways. This means there are many things to know about a word, and we can know it to different degrees. Nation (2022) identifies nine aspects of word knowledge and divides each aspect into receptive and productive knowledge. He believes receptive vocabulary use means understanding the form of a word when we hear or read it and knowing what it means. In contrast, productive vocabulary use means expressing meaning when we speak or write and using the correct spoken or written word form. According to Nation (2022), understanding a word involves the following 18 aspects of vocabulary knowledge from both receptive and productive perspectives:

Receptive Knowledge:

1. Recognizing pronunciation and sound.
2. Familiarity with written form.
3. Understanding word parts (prefix, stem, suffix).
4. Knowing the core common meaning.
5. Grasping meaning in specific contexts.
6. Recognizing related words.
7. Identifying correct usage in sentences.
8. Recognizing typical co-occurring words (collocations).
9. Awareness of commonness and connotations (inferred meanings).

Productive Knowledge:

1. Correctly pronouncing with appropriate stress.
2. Spelling and writing correctly.
3. Constructing using correct word parts.
4. Expressing meaning.
5. Using in various contexts.
6. Producing synonyms and opposites.
7. Using correctly in sentences.
8. Producing co-occurring words (collocations).
9. Considering formality and appropriateness.

Teaching Vocabulary

Nation (2022) asserts that the role of instructing vocabulary should be limited in the vocabulary learning process, not exceeding a quarter of a course. Teachers need to exercise caution to prevent an excessive focus on this role, ensuring a balanced allocation of time for both intentional and incidental vocabulary learning. Nation outlines three pivotal considerations for direct vocabulary instruction in language learning.

Firstly, the instruction should primarily focus on teaching the high-frequency vocabulary of the language, including the Academic Word List (AWL) for learners with academic goals. The benefits of learning high-frequency words justify the time spent on direct vocabulary instruction. Secondly, direct vocabulary instruction should be seen as just one aspect of a comprehensive course, occupying a small portion of the overall course duration. Thirdly, while direct instruction is effective for certain aspects of word knowledge, some elements rely on experience and implicit understanding rather than explicit teaching. This makes alternative methods more effective for those specific aspects.

Consequently, instructors should establish realistic objectives for vocabulary instruction, focusing specifically on high-frequency words, emphasizing critical aspects of word knowledge, and allocating minimal time to individual words.

Learning Vocabulary

Vocabulary learning can extend beyond the classroom in three contexts. First context (Extramural Learning, Sundqvist & Sylvén, 2016) involves unintentional learning through entertainment like TV, movies, the internet, online social interactions, digital games, music, and digital reading. It is independent of formal English courses. The second context (Extra-Curricular Learning, Benson, 2011) occurs outside the classroom but relates to classroom courses. It is guided by instructors or initiated by learners to complement classroom learning. Activities include extensive reading, listening, interactions, writing, and deliberate vocabulary learning. The third context (Self-Directed Learning, see Nation & Yamamoto, 2012) involves learners independently structuring language learning without a teacher's involvement. This involves learning English on your own, without the help of a teacher, and it could involve using online resources or talking to native speakers.

While technology expands the possibilities for vocabulary learning, it should be viewed as a tool rather than a magic solution. Effort is still required to learn new words. Learning through entertainment, such as gaming and social media, often involves incidental learning. For instance, exposure to pop songs can contribute significantly to acquiring a substantial portion of the most frequent words. Displaying song lyrics while listening supports deliberate learning, and activities like karaoke or reading and singing lyrics can further enhance vocabulary acquisition (Pavia et al., 2019).

Graded Readers and Flashcards

Intentional vocabulary learning is an efficient way to build vocabulary, especially when combined with incidental learning from everyday tasks and conversations, leading to a quicker grasp of new words (Vandenberghe et al., 2021). Two effective tools for intentional vocabulary learning are graded readers and flashcards.

Graded readers are well-crafted texts designed with a limited vocabulary and organized into different tiers. For example, the [Oxford Bookworms](#) series from Oxford University Press presents six tiers, ranging from 400 to 2,500 words. Readers with a vocabulary of under 400 words can comfortably engage with level-one books, encountering only a few unfamiliar terms worth learning at that stage. Following the recommendation of Nation and Wang (1999), it is beneficial for learners to read approximately five books at a specific level from the Oxford Bookworms series.

These graded readers primarily concentrate on high-frequency words, especially the 3,000 most frequent ones. However, mid-frequency readers are specifically created for more advanced learners with a vocabulary ranging from 4,000 to 8,000 words (Nation & Anthony, 2013). You can find these readers on [Paul Nation's repository](#). Additionally, more free graded readers can be accessed at [Free Graded Readers](#).

Flashcards, or word cards, have the target word in one language on one side and its meaning or synonym on the other. Flashcards promote active recall by retrieving the meaning of the newly learned words from the memory. Seeing a word and then actively trying to remember its meaning helps keep newly learned words in mind. Modern flashcard apps like [Anki](#) and [Quizlet](#) are better than paper cards as they help track progress, customize timing, and include pictures and audio for better learning.

Vocabulary Testing

Diagnostic and Placement Tests

Diagnostic tests help identify which levels of word frequency learners may lack form-meaning knowledge. These tests are essential for guiding teachers and learners in making informed decisions about their learning journey. The Vocabulary Levels Test (VLT) is a widely used diagnostic tool known for its versatility. It assesses learners' form-meaning knowledge across different word levels, ranging from 1,000 to 5,000 (including academic words in updated versions).

Updated versions of the VLT, developed by McLean and Kramer (2015) and Webb, Sasao, and Ballance (2017), focus on evaluating high-frequency and valuable mid-frequency words. These tests are accessible through [Paul Nation's repository](#). The online version of Webb, Sasao, and Ballance's (2017) VLT is available on [Stuart Webb's repository](#).

The VLT is useful for placing low-proficiency EFL learners, while advanced learners may find the Vocabulary Size Test (VST) or its bilingual versions more beneficial. The VST, developed by Beglar (2010) and Nation & Beglar (2007), measures overall vocabulary size in two versions: 14,000 and 20,000 word levels. In the 14,000-word version, there are 140 multiple-choice items, and the total score (multiplied by 100) determines the learner's total receptive vocabulary size. The 20,000-word versions have 100 items each, and the total score (multiplied by 200) provides the total receptive vocabulary size. You can access the VST on [Paul Nation's repository](#) and an [online platform](#). However, it is worth noting that the multiple-choice format of the VST may lead to excessive guessing by less proficient learners, as observed by Stoeckel, McLean, and Nation (2020), making it less suitable for them.

Achievement Tests

Short-term achievement tests focus on recently studied words, typically over the past week or two, drawn directly from course materials. These tests offer feedback to both teachers and learners on the success of recent learning efforts. They do not gauge overall vocabulary size or guide future learning but serve as a prompt assessment tool.

According to Nation (2022), short-term achievement tests should possess specific characteristics: Ease of Creation (for simplicity in test generation), Ease of Grading (to provide quick feedback to learners), and Fairness (to align with recent course content and not overwhelm learners with too many expectations for a limited learning time). Examples of such tests can be found in Nation's *learning vocabulary in another language*, notably on page 475.

Long-term achievement tests are usually administered at a course's end, with mid-course tests in longer courses to track progress. When selecting words for long-term achievement tests, the teacher should consider their intended purpose, typically grading and course evaluation. These tests should draw from the course's covered vocabulary, providing a reasonable representation of words encountered throughout the course. One approach is to select words from each week's lessons or units of study.

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